

BUILDING LITERACY OF LITERARY CULTURE OF CRITICISM AMONG STUDENTS

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There's a tendency for students in schools to focus solely on reading and writing, without balancing it with, or at least interspersing, material on literary criticism. Yet, if students write or present literary works without (attempting to) critique them, they won't be able to evaluate the works they read, or the works they write themselves. This leads to a "blindness" regarding the development of Indonesian literature, or even the development of their own writing.

To foster a culture of literary criticism among students, teachers must play a key role in guiding their students. Teachers can take the initial step of cultivating this culture of criticism by integrating literary criticism material into their regular literature lessons without any special conditioning, thus not altering the existing learning environment. This (non-special conditioning) is only applicable if the learning environment has been previously structured to stimulate the development of students' knowledge and creativity in literature.

This culture of critical thinking can be initiated by the supervising teacher by giving students an assignment to write a literary work, then having them present their work to the class. Afterward, the teacher can begin their role gradually, starting with providing input, suggestions, and appreciation, eventually leading to criticism of the student's work.

It's important to note that teachers must be careful when providing criticism to prevent students from feeling offended or discouraged—let alone discouraged from writing again—after receiving criticism of their work. This is important to note and implement because, in general, novice writers at the student/teenage level quickly feel inferior when their work is criticized by someone, especially if the criticism is perceived as somewhat "sharp." Teachers should be able to understand this, considering the nature or characteristics of teenagers who are easily swayed in their stance and quickly frustrated.

To avoid undesirable outcomes like those outlined above, teachers can consider alternatives by first explaining the nature of literary criticism to students. Alternatively, they can package the criticism in a "respectful" format appropriate for the students. This explanation and formatting will help students understand the importance and role of criticism in the development of literature itself, further stimulating their continued writing. Teachers can also explain the existence of several prominent literary critics and their roles in the development of literature, or explore the romance of literary criticism in Indonesia.

Inter-Student Discussion

After the teacher has implemented these initial steps, the next step is to invite students to critique the work of their peers. This kind of student-to-student literary criticism can be structured as a class discussion. In this discussion, students can express their criticism of each other's work, and vice versa. This fosters interaction between students, which will then guide them toward learning to critique others' literary works. This certainly makes for an engaging learning experience for students.

Furthermore, while still in the discussion mode, teachers can also guide students to begin learning to critique literary works in textbooks or works by authors published in books or in the media. Here, teachers are indirectly guiding students toward a reading culture, which is the foundation for successfully developing a critical culture among students.

In this case, in addition to guiding the discussion, teachers should continuously provide guidance and direction to their students regarding literary criticism. Teachers should also act as neutral parties, enabling them to guide each student without taking sides, even if there are similar perceptions between the teacher and the students regarding the work being critiqued.

Writing and Media

Teacher intervention in this regard must also be limited. Teachers must not influence their students' critical areas and creativity. Critical areas and creativity should be the absolute property of the students. Guidance should not delve too far, let alone enter these areas. If that happens, the teacher's role is no longer an educator, but rather a destroyer of the students' critical areas and creativity. In other words, teachers must guide students toward independence.

The next step that the supervising teacher should take is to guide students in putting the literary criticism they've developed in the previous discussion into written form. Teachers can provide students with literature on literary criticism that can serve as references or examples for writing. This literature can be taken from newspapers or books, which are widely available today. A guidebook for writing literary criticism is also crucial here.

When using literature as an example of how to write literary criticism, the supervising teacher should pay attention to the level of complexity of the literary criticism contained within the literature. Students should avoid being presented with literature containing highly complex criticism, which could confuse or create a sense of misunderstanding. The literature used should be used solely as an example, not as something to be imitated. Again, teachers must guide students toward independence in exploring their own critical and creative areas.

To encourage students' enthusiasm for literary criticism, the existence of a medium, such as a wall magazine, to publish their writings seems essential. This medium is crucial because it will

stimulate new discourses about literature among students. This situation is certainly very interesting and demonstrates the increasing development of literature learning in schools.

Once the conditioning of literary criticism publications among students is underway, media development can be used as a benchmark for the development of a culture of literary criticism among students. At this stage, students can begin to be guided toward inter-student literary criticism competitions.

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